

In silico models in oncology, neurology, and epidemiology:
systems-level and multiscale perspectives

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Abstract

Computational and *in silico* medicine has emerged as a central paradigm for studying complex diseases, driven by advances in mathematical modelling, high-performance computing, and the availability of large-scale biomedical data. Many pathological processes—from tumour evolution and brain dysfunction to epidemic spread—are inherently multiscale, nonlinear, and shaped by interactions across molecular, cellular, tissue, and population levels, making them particularly suited to systems-level approaches.

In this review, we synthesize recent developments in *in silico* oncology, neurology, and epidemiology, showing how computational frameworks are used to investigate disease mechanisms, predict outcomes, and support applications such as personalized cancer therapy, digital brain and neuromodulation modelling, and epidemic forecasting and control. Despite addressing distinct clinical questions, these fields share a common methodological foundation grounded in Systems and Control theory, hybrid and data-

driven modelling, and the analysis of complex, networked dynamics. We highlight how mechanistic, statistical, and machine-learning approaches are combined to integrate heterogeneous data and capture emergent disease behaviour across scales.

Beyond summarizing domain-specific advances and shared paradigms, we identify key barriers that limit clinical translation, including challenges in model calibration and validation, uncertainty quantification, data integration, interpretability, and reproducibility. We conclude by outlining emerging directions—such as digital twins, adaptive and evolution-aware control strategies, and hybrid mechanistic–machine learning workflows—that are expected to further integrate *in silico* models into biomedical research and healthcare, supporting a shift toward predictive, personalized, and systems-driven medicine, and reinforcing the role of *in silico* approaches as a transformative paradigm in biomedical research and clinical practice.

Key words: *in silico* models, complexity science, disease modelling, nonlinear dynamics, personalized treatments, multidisciplinary approaches, systems and control

1 Introduction

In recent decades, the intersection of mathematical modelling, computational tools, data analytics, and medical science has engendered a profound transformation in healthcare research and clinical practice. This evolution has culminated in the emergence of computational and *in silico* medicine, a multi-faceted discipline leveraging the utilization of sophisticated computational methodologies to simulate, analyse, and forecast the behaviour of biological systems [1, 2]. This paradigm shift has not only expanded our comprehension of intricate disease mechanisms but also revolutionized therapeutic modalities for complex pathological conditions.

Within the expansive domain of *in silico* medicine, oncology [3, 4], neurology [5, 6], and epidemiology [7, 8] have emerged as prominent fields of inquiry, each presenting distinct challenges and opportunities for computational approaches. Despite their disparate focuses, these disciplines share a fundamental underpinning: they all benefit from the application of systems theory and the principles and tools of complexity science to elucidate their intricate nonlinear dynamics [9]. By adopting a holistic perspective that integrates different time and space scales, *in silico* methodologies offer a comprehensive framework to investigate the subtleties of disease progression and pathophysiology, and to translate models into clinical practice [10].

For instance, *in silico* oncology employs computational models to simulate the biology of cancers, encompassing tumour growth, evolutionary dynamics of arising clones, spatio-temporal intratumour heterogeneity, metastatic dissemination, and therapeutic response profiles, among others. These models facilitate the design of optimal personalized treatment combinations [11, 12] and schedules [13], and support the discovery [14] and repurposing [15] of effective therapeutic agents and novel biomarkers [16]. Likewise, computational

neurology endeavors to elucidate the intricate network dynamics of the central nervous system [17], shedding light on the pathogenesis of neurological afflictions such as Alzheimer’s [18] and Parkinson’s [19] diseases, and Restless Legs Syndrome [20]. These insights inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at alleviating disease burden and enhancing patient outcomes. Concurrently, computational epidemiology [7] harnesses predictive modelling and data-driven analytics to forecast disease outbreaks [21], evaluate intervention strategies [22], and optimise public health policies [23]. Notably, recent endeavors in this domain have been particularly important to mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic [24, 25].

This review aims to synthesize the wealth of knowledge accrued across these three diverse domains, elucidating the transformative potential of *in silico* medicine in reshaping contemporary healthcare paradigms. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and leveraging state-of-the-art computational methodologies, we envision a future wherein computational models serve as indispensable tools for understanding disease mechanisms, informing clinical decision-making, and advancing the boundaries of precision medicine.

In the following sections, we provide a structured overview of recent advances in *in silico* and computational medicine in the three before-mentioned fields: oncology, neurology, and epidemiology. The literature was surveyed using major bibliographic databases (Web of Science and Scopus), focusing on recent and representative contributions in computational and *in silico* oncology, neurology, and epidemiology. Rather than a systematic review, this work provides a narrative, concept-driven synthesis emphasizing shared modelling paradigms, translational challenges, and emerging directions.

Thus, the structure of the article is as follows: Section 1 corresponds to the introduction of the article, as we have just outlined. Section 2 is the core part of this review and focuses on the various *in silico* results that have been obtained in the literature. Section 2.1 focuses on *in silico* results in the field of oncology. Section 2.2 focuses on the different *in silico* approaches obtained in the field of neurology, and Section 2.3 reviews the results obtained for epidemiology. Section 2.4 offers a comprehensive overview bringing these three fields together, by highlighting their common paradigms and their shared bottlenecks. Finally, Section 3 summarizes the main conclusions from this overview of the state-of-the-art of *in silico* computational approaches in the three fields studied: oncology, neurology, and epidemiology.

2 Results

2.1 *In silico* oncology

Cancer is a major global health challenge, with profound socio-economic impact that affect millions of lives [26]. Actually, the World Health Organization (WHO) states that cancer is the major cause of death globally [27]. According to the most recent estimates from the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), there were nearly 20 million new cancer cases and 9.7 million cancer-related deaths worldwide in 2022 [26].

Figure 1: Cancer incidence (a) and mortality (b) in 2022: 20.0 million new cases and 9.7 million deaths. Maps show country-level age-standardized rates (ASR), while pie charts display the distribution by cancer type based on absolute numbers. Lung cancer is the leading contributor in both incidence and mortality (12.4% and 18.7%, respectively), followed by colorectal (9.6% and 9.3%), breast (11.6% and 7.8%), liver (4.3% and 7.8%), and stomach cancer (4.9% and 6.8%). Prostate, thyroid, bladder, and non-Hodgkin lymphoma are among the most frequent cancers in incidence only (a), whereas pancreatic, esophageal cancers, and leukemia appear among the leading causes of mortality only (b). Cervical cancer is present in both incidence and mortality (3.3% and 3.6%, respectively). Remaining cancers account for 36.6% of cases and 30.3% of deaths. ASR refers to a weighted average of age-specific rates per 100,000 people, where weights correspond to the population distribution across age groups. Data from the Global Cancer Observatory of the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) [26, 28]. Figure adapted from [29].

These numbers indicate that about one in five individuals will develop cancer during their lifetime, while approximately one in nine men and one in twelve women will die from it. Figure 1 shows global cancer

incidence and mortality in 2022 by countries and by cancer types, respectively. Thus, understanding the growth and evolution of cancers and how to exploit them in optimal treatments is an important open question [30] that could benefit from the contributions of mathematics [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37].

Figure 2: Cancer hallmarks (inside the gray circle) as reported in the original framework by Hanahan and Weinberg [38, 39], complemented with representative associations to *in silico* modelling approaches (outside the gray circle and within the same two radii), e.g., hybrid models for the hallmark of activating invasion and metastasis. The associations shown are not intended to be exhaustive, but rather to provide a conceptual mapping of plausible relationships.

The transformation of healthy cells into tumour cells takes multiple steps, starting from a pre-cancerous lesion up to a malignant tumour [27]. This evolutionary process, better known as carcinogenesis, has never been explicitly tracked *in vivo*, and despite there is consensus regarding the mechanism whereby it occurs

(the somatic mutation theory [40]), its exact unfolding is still subject of debate [41]. It is widely accepted that several key modifications (namely, *driver mutations*) are required for a healthy cell to promote to an unrestrained growth state, which, if uncontrolled, may eventually give rise to a tumour. These modifications are the result of the combined effect of the subject's genetic characteristics and external environmental influences, i.e., physical, chemical, and biological carcinogens [27]. This interplay of factors is one of the reasons why cancer is considered one of the most dynamic and complex groups of diseases.

To make matters worse, cancers can invade or spread to other tissues or organs, which are not always nearby (in contrast with benign tumours, which lack this invasive potential. This contributes substantially to cancer-related mortality. This invasiveness is but one of cancer hallmarks [38, 39]. There has been a recent effort to characterize the most relevant cancer trademarks, which encompass replicative immortality (each cell can potentially duplicate infinite times), genome instability (high mutation rate), evasion of growth-suppressor signals, sustained proliferation, resist cellular death, avoid immune destruction, altered metabolism, cancer-promoting inflammation, angiogenesis, and activation of invasion and metastases [38] together with emerging enabling features including unlocking phenotypic plasticity, nonmutational epigenetic reprogramming, the accumulation of senescent cells, and polymorphic microbiomes [39] (Figure 2).

Clinically speaking, the choice of treatment depends on the type and stage of cancer, as well as on individual patient factors. The main types of cancer treatments include surgery [42, 43], radiation therapy [44, 45, 46, 47, 48], immunotherapy [49, 50, 51], chemotherapy [52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59], targeted therapy [60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65], personalized medicine [66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71], nanotherapy [72, 73, 74, 75, 76], oncolytic virus [77, 78, 79, 80, 81], and many more.

Whenever possible, these treatment options help either removing completely the malignant tumour cells or, at least, controlling their growth pace. Unfortunately, clinical practice often falls short when it comes to thoroughly explore the effect of different treatment schemes, due to small sample sizes, high inter-patient heterogeneity, and the lack of untreated controls (which would be ethically dubious). To help overcoming these shortcomings, we have *in silico* oncology. Indeed, *in silico* oncology applies many different suitable methodologies to different specific research problems. These important studies bring new insight into cancer biology [82], evolution [12, 83, 84, 13], clinical [85] and also both pre-clinical [86] and post-clinical [87] information, bio-markers identification [88], treatment [12, 84, 13, 89, 47, 89, 76, 90], and even prevention [91]. Recently, computational-based patents, tackling some relevant cancer treatment aspects, have been successfully proposed [92].

Among all the different suitable methodologies that *in silico* oncology exploit, we can start by mentioning network-based approaches. Network science has been highly applied to model cancer inter- and intracellular communications [93, 11], i.e., pathways and signal transduction, starting from the simpler Boolean networks up to more complex differential equation and Bayesian networks [94, 95, 96]. Moreover, lattices

and even more intricate networks are exploited to model interconnections among the agents (sub-populations [13, 90] or single cells [84]), adding a spatial or functional structure to the model. Since cancer cells are deeply intertwined and constantly communicating (even with non-cancer cells in their surroundings, like cancer-associated fibroblasts in the tumour microenvironment [97]) and exchanging signaling molecules, these network-based approaches help us untie the convoluted web of interactions intrinsic to tumours.

Virtual screening techniques, such as the one illustrated by Zhu *et al.* [98], accelerate the identification of novel anti-cancer compounds. Moreover, in numerous cancer types, the utilization of drug repurposing [65, 15] and drug combinations [99, 100] have demonstrated enhanced durability and reduced resistance to existing first-line therapies. However, the conventional (*in vitro* and *in vivo*) approaches to drug discovery are characterized by prohibitive costs and work [101]. To address this challenge, there is an urgent need for computational methods that can effectively model the intricate interactions of drug target pathways and identify the underlying mechanisms driving the synergistic effects of drug combinations. An example of this approach is the SynGeNet (Synergy from Gene expression and Network mining) method [11], which integrates transcriptomics-based connectivity mapping and network centrality analysis to study disease networks and predict the efficacy of drug combinations.

Pharmacophore modelling [102, 103], a subfield of structural biology and computational chemistry, predicts the 3D arrangement of molecular features necessary for a drug to bind to its target protein, identifying potential drugs that may selectively inhibit cancer-specific targets. Molecular docking predicts the binding interaction between a small molecule (e.g., a drug) and its target protein at the atomic level. This method helps in screening and prioritizing potential drugs, evaluating also toxicological effects [104]. Also, molecular dynamics simulations, whereby protein movements at the atom level are modelled using classical mechanics (and sometimes even quantum effects for local interactions), are of relevance for easing the drug discovery and screening processes. This method is useful for validating binding modes predicted by molecular docking, for mapping target proteins hot-spots, and for generating protein conformation ensembles for *in silico* drug design [14].

Bioinformatics, and more specifically, omics studies, are commonly used for data mining in cancer (and genetic diseases in general) research. Bioinformatics encompasses such a wide field, covering a plethora of different techniques and approaches to biological data. To narrow it down, the main areas of interest within bioinformatics cover the development and analysis of algorithms to process biological information, the design of databases to store, connect and contextualize vast amounts of data (sourcing from DNA sequences, protein structures or gene expression profiles), and the study of statistical methods to distil meaningful insights from biological data. Processing high-throughput biological information and creating adequate databases to store it has resulted in the development of omics (from classical genomics, proteomics, and transcriptomics, to more recent additions such as lipidomics, epigenomics, and metabolomics), which have substantially speeded

research in oncology, but have also raised new problems and concerns, mostly about data integration and representation, and dimensionality reduction [105]. The contextualization of previous data has resulted in useful initiatives aimed at coherently and controllably annotate and label biological entities, such as the gene ontology database [106], which allows to identify a gene’s/protein’s function and location, enabling fast interpretation of multiplexed data. The integration of bioinformatics with oncology not only lets us build knowledge about the disease, but also personalize treatments and come closer to a real precision oncology [107]. Specific goals are to profile cancer cells and their microenvironment, e.g., for target therapy [11] and immunotherapeutic discovery [108].

In the last few years, Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods have been proposed in the literature with the potential to transform oncology [109] (and medicine in general), enabling the prediction of drug response, enhancing theranostics [110], aiding in personalized treatment selection, and improving not only nanomedicine [76], but also the detection of cancers [111]. These approaches now increasingly exploit multimodal and multi-omics integration (combining imaging, histopathology, genomics, transcriptomics and clinical data) to derive richer, patient-specific signatures that improve diagnosis, prognostication and therapy selection [112]. Deep learning models and specialized libraries (for example frameworks designed for drug-response prediction) have shown promising performance in predicting tumour sensitivity and resistance patterns from genomic and pharmacological datasets, although benchmarking and standardization remain challenging [113, 114]. In theranostics, AI is being applied to automate image segmentation, perform patient selection and to improve dosimetry and treatment planning for radiopharmaceuticals, potentially enabling more precise, individualized theranostic workflows [115, 116]. In nanomedicine, ML accelerates nanoparticle design, predicts biodistribution and toxicity, and helps to optimise formulation and delivery—approaches that are shortening the design-test cycle for nanoscale therapeutics and theranostics [117, 17]. Other active lines of development include federated learning and privacy-preserving training (to share models across hospitals without centralizing sensitive data), explainable AI methods (to increase clinical trustworthiness) and physics/knowledge-informed ML that embed prior mechanistic knowledge to improve generalisability [118, 119]. Nonetheless, important barriers persist—data heterogeneity, limited annotated clinical datasets for many tumour types, issues of model interpretability, prospective clinical validation and regulatory approval are active areas of research that must be addressed before broad clinical deployment [120, 121].

More recently, advances in computational pathology and spatial omics are increasingly redefining how deep representation learning is grounded in biological reality, with explicit modelling of spatial relationships and entropy-based complexity measures emerging as key anchoring mechanisms. Rather than treating tissues as texture-rich but topologically flat images, modern workflows abstract samples into spatial point processes—cells or spots with defined coordinates and phenotypic identities—thereby making cell–cell proximity, neighborhood structure, and multiscale organisation explicit analytical objects. By encoding who

interacts with whom, and at what spatial scale, spatial descriptors shift representation learning away from purely appearance-driven correlations toward features that correspond to known microenvironmental processes, including immune exclusion, invasion fronts, and stromal remodelling [122].

Within this spatially explicit framework, entropy-based measures provide a principled bridge between tissue organisation and deep learning representations by quantifying heterogeneity, disorder, and complexity across scales [123]. Entropy metrics capture not only compositional diversity but, critically, the organisation of that diversity in space, distinguishing structured microenvironments from chaotic or transitional states. Since entropy abstracts complex spatial configurations into scale-agnostic measures of order and uncertainty, it enables deep models to encode tissue ecology rather than dataset-specific artifacts. Collectively, the coupling of spatial relationship extraction with entropy-based complexity metrics reframes deep representation learning as an ecological observer of biological microenvironments, ensuring that computational models remain anchored to mechanistically interpretable patterns of tissue organisation while retaining the flexibility and predictive power of modern deep learning.

Complementing this, adaptive multimodal fusion mechanisms are emerging as a powerful paradigm for integrating such spatial representations with deep networks. Notably, entropy-guided hybrid architectures that dynamically fuse GNN-based (graph neural networks) local topology with state-space models such as Mamba demonstrate how predictive uncertainty can be used to balance local and global information on a per-sample basis, avoiding rigid fusion assumptions and enabling scalable modelling of complex, heterogeneous tissues [124]. Together, these developments illustrate a broader shift toward uncertainty-aware, spatially grounded, and dynamically reconfigurable AI systems that parallel and inform advances in multimodal integration across multi-omics research.

Multiscale *in silico* models—with scales spanning from biomolecules and metabolites up to tissues and entire patient bodies—provide a powerful framework for understanding cancer growth and therapy response [125, 70]. In Table 1, we provide an updated and extended taxonomy of evolutionary cancer models, building upon the framework previously established in [84], introducing two significant advancements. First, in addition to population-based (PB) and cell-based (CB) models, we have introduced a specific category for Hybrid (H) models: these couple a CB and PB approach by using a discrete individual-based description for cancer cells with continuous dynamics for the diffusion of oxygen, nutrients, and/or drugs. We detail the three categories hereafter. Consequently, several models previously classified as purely CB in [84] have been repositioned to better reflect their nature. Second, recent state-of-the-art references have been added and discussed.

Population-Based (PB) models describe cancer cells as homogeneous populations or structured sub-populations through continuous variables [90, 126, 127, 13, 128, 129, 130, 131, 132, 133]. While they are amenable to formal mathematical analysis and optimal control theory—making them essential for linking

macroscopic clinical data to mechanistic parameters [134, 135]—they often lack the resolution to capture fine-grained stochasticity, since they are more fit to capture the averaged behaviour of large ensembles of interacting cells/agents. It is possible to formally derive them from CB models [136].

Cell-Based (CB) models, or agent/individual-based models, treat each cell as an independent unit [137, 138, 84]. This allows for a high-fidelity representation of genetic heterogeneity and emergent phenomena like clonal selection [139, 140], though at a higher computational cost [141], and by limiting the scale of the simulation, making it difficult to simulate the number of cells present in tumours of clinically relevant size.

Hybrid (H) models represent the synthesis of these approaches [142, 143, 67, 144, 63, 145, 146, 147]. By combining individual cell descriptions with continuum formalisms for the microenvironment, they serve as the backbone for modern digital twin approaches [148, 135]. As shown in Table 1, these models are increasingly used to manage the trade-off between model complexity and realism versus computational tractability and interpretability of results.

In Table 1, we refer to multiscale models that include adaptive resistance to treatments (i.e. phenotypes describing the type and level of cancer resistance to a treatment), reporting the list of references with the model basic features. All models mentioned in Table 1 have been used to investigate the interplay between different control strategies and the adaptive response of cancer to treatment. In particular, such models provide the theoretical foundation for adaptive and metronomic regimens that aim to preserve drug-sensitive competitors and delay resistant takeover, a strategy supported by both mathematical studies and preclinical/clinical work [152, 153, 154]. Detailed CB and H models are so complex, typically designed in a stochastic framework, that they can be solved only through numerical simulation. However, they have the potential to match *in vitro*, *in vivo*, or clinical case studies and provide reliable predictions [67, 141, 63]. Indeed, in all CB (except for work [84]) and H cases, different control strategies have been compared in terms of a target of interest, such as cancer size at the end or during treatment, without facing the heavy computational challenge of optimal control in the CB framework (No optimal strategy, ‘N’ in Table 1). Instead, in some cases of PB, the search for the optimal strategy has been carried out (‘Y’ in Table 1).

Among PB evolutionary models, the unstructured framework proposed by Orlando, Gatenby, and Brown [53] represents a seminal contribution to the study of treatment-driven cancer evolution. Despite its simplicity, this model introduced the concept of exploiting resistance trade-offs through an evolutionary double bind [155], whereby adaptation to one cytotoxic drug increases susceptibility to another. By explicitly modelling drug-specific resistance allocation, the framework demonstrated how evolutionary constraints can be leveraged to design treatment strategies that delay resistance emergence.

Subsequent studies have reinforced the potential of double-bind and trade-off-based strategies, showing that sequential or adaptive schedules can outperform classical maximum-tolerated-dose regimens in heterogeneous tumours *in silico* [156, 157, 158, 13]. Importantly, later work highlighted that incorporating

Table 1: Literature review of Population-Based (PB), Cell-Based (CB), and Hybrid (H) evolutionary models. The table highlights the modelling of the resistance phenotype (D for discrete vs. C for continuous) and whether optimal strategies have been investigated (Y for yes vs. N for no). This table is adapted and extended from [84], introducing the new Hybrid (H) category and incorporating recent literature.

Ref.	Model Type	Resist. Phen.	Opt. Strat.	Notes
[90]	PB	D	N	<i>In silico</i> trials for malignant glioma patients under chemotherapy and immunotherapy.
[126]	PB	D	N	Leukemia model linking relapse risk to initial chemotherapy response.
[127]	PB	D	N	<i>In silico</i> trials for low grade gliomas under temozolomide overcoming drug resistance.
[130]	PB	D	N	Pre-existing vs. induced resistance in slow-growing tumours.
[133]	PB	D	N	<i>In silico</i> trials for malignant glioma patients under chemotherapy and radiotherapy.
[149]	PB	D	N	Spatiotemporal cell growth dynamics and response to doxorubicin in breast cancer.
[150]	PB	D	Y	<i>In vitro</i> experiments and game-theory model for double-bind in breast cancer.
[128]	PB	D	Y	Optimal control strategies for drug resistance.
[129]	PB	D	Y	Evolutionary dynamics and optimal control to manage drug resistance in cancer therapy.
[13]	PB	D/C	Y	Minimization of neuroblastoma under two drugs (D for genetic resistance, C for plastic).
[132]	PB	C	N	Dynamics of a structured PB model endowed with constrained plasticity of traits.
[131]	PB	C	Y	Optimizing therapy for tumour reduction under a drug-resistance continuum.
[137]	CB	D	N	Prostate cancer model studying intra-tumoural competition during adaptive therapy.
[138]	CB	D	N	BRAF-mutated melanoma model investigating growth rate and phenotypic adaptation.
[151]	CB	D	Y	Analysis of temozolomide schemes for gliomas with extended spacing between doses.
[84]	CB	C	Y	Optimal two-drug treatment with trade-offs in allocation of drug-specific resistance.
[142]	H	D	N	Multiscale model of macrophage polarization in glioma and therapeutic implications.
[143]	H	D	N	Analysis of angiogenesis-induced resistance in brain tumours with combined treatments.
[67]	H	D	N	Cell cycle dynamics in a vascularized tumour under chemo-radiotherapy.
[144]	H	D	N	Interplay among intracellular, extracellular, and intercellular factors in drug resistance.
[63]	H	D	N	Role of the spatial structure on the effectiveness of static and adaptive chemotherapies.
[145]	H	D	N	Vascular impact on tumour evolution and thermal therapy outcomes.
[146]	H	D	N	Multi-scale neuroblastoma model for patient-specific simulations.
[147]	H	C	N	Metabolic heterogeneity effect on vascularized tumour growth under different therapies.

pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics and spatial structure can qualitatively alter selective pressures and optimal control policies, underscoring the limitations of well-mixed assumptions [159, 158, 160].

Within this evolutionary perspective, adaptive therapy has emerged as a prominent paradigm that shifts treatment goals from eradication to long-term control by dynamically adjusting dosing in response to tumour evolution [152]. Initially explored *in silico* [161, 154], adaptive therapy represents one of the clearest examples of a mathematically motivated strategy that has progressed to clinical testing, including trials in prostate cancer [162].

Nevertheless, open challenges remain regarding model design, protocol validation, and clinical imple-

mentation [163]. Building on these population-based foundations, our work extended the Orlando *et al.* framework to a cell-based setting to assess the robustness of optimal control strategies under genetic heterogeneity, spatial competition, and stochasticity [84]. By retaining sufficient phenotypic complexity while relaxing homogeneity assumptions, this approach demonstrated how candidate control policies identified in reduced PB models can be critically reassessed in more realistic multiscale contexts. In particular, incorporating spatial structure and pharmacokinetic constraints, together with discrete dosing and monitoring schedules reflecting clinical practice, was shown to alter the class of optimal solutions, often favouring adaptive or pulsed protocols [164, 159]. Comparative PB–CB analyses further support the use of multiscale *in silico* frameworks to evaluate the translational robustness of evolution-aware treatment strategies [158, 165].

Instead, in [13], a population-based model of neuroblastoma treated with vincristine and cyclophosphamide—two standard agents in the COJEC protocol [58]—was developed to explore how tumour composition and resistance phenotypes influence optimal treatment strategies. By considering distinct initial tumour states as virtual patients, this framework illustrates how *in silico* models can support the investigation of personalized therapy design under treatment-induced evolutionary pressure.

Indeed, diagnosis and treatment strategies based on personalized or precision medicine are achieving increasing interest thanks to the potential applicability of engineered studies in many medical fields, especially in oncology, where personalized medicine seems to be the most promising approach against treatment failures [67, 71], also in an evolutionary modelling framework [83].

Recent developments have reinforced this trend by showing that precision oncology is no longer limited to single-gene markers but increasingly relies on multi-omics integration, liquid biopsies, and comprehensive biomarker signatures that combine genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, and imaging-derived features to define patient-specific therapeutic windows [166, 16]. These advances have driven new clinical-trial designs (basket, umbrella and platform trials) and molecular tumour boards that operationalize personalised decisions in the clinic, enabling rapid matching of patients to targeted agents or combination strategies [167, 168].

From a modelling perspective, evolutionary and adaptive-therapy frameworks provide a natural bridge between precision diagnostics and treatment scheduling: by explicitly modelling intra-tumour heterogeneity and competitive interactions among subpopulations, evolutionary models can propose adaptive dosing schedules that prolong control and delay resistance compared with fixed maximum-tolerated-dose policies [158]. Notably, clinical and *in silico* studies have demonstrated that model-informed adaptive protocols can increase time to progression in some settings, underscoring the translational potential of combining patient-specific data with evolutionary control algorithms [162, 163].

Moreover, recent work highlights two essential modelling ingredients for truly personalised *in silico* predictions: (i) explicit incorporation of pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics (PK/PD) and (ii) calibration to

patient-specific longitudinal biomarkers (e.g., ctDNA dynamics, imaging volumetrics). Including PK/PD constrains the timing and magnitude of selective pressures, while longitudinal biomarker calibration enables real-time updating of model parameters for closed-loop adaptive strategies [159, 169]. Together, these ingredients improve the reliability of model-based treatment recommendations and pave the way for hybrid workflows that combine mechanistic models, statistical emulators, and machine-learning surrogates to produce clinically actionable, patient-tailored schedules [170, 160].

Finally, the convergence of precision diagnostics, flexible trial designs, and evolution-aware modelling suggests a practical route to test personalised, model-informed therapies: integrate multi-omic profiling and frequent minimally invasive monitoring (liquid biopsy), use evolutionary models to propose candidate adaptive protocols, and evaluate them in biomarker-driven platform trials that allow rapid iteration between model prediction and clinical observation [167, 169, 171]. All these highlight the relevance of mechanistic modelling and mechanistic learning in computational oncology [172]. The conceptual pipeline for such an integrated multiscale approach is detailed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Multiscale framework for *in silico* oncology. The workflow integrates biological knowledge and data from different time- and spatial-scales (from DNA and Omics data, to longitudinal biomarker and pharmacokinetics, up to imaging and patient survival) into a computational framework. The latter is a cell-based (CB), population-based (PB), or hybrid (H) model, see Table 1 for evolutionary models. The Physics-Informed ML layer acts as a surrogate model, trained on high-fidelity simulations to achieve model acceleration for real-time predictive pipelines. Finally, the framework supports closed-loop control, such as adaptive therapy, where clinical outputs and resistance patterns are fed back (dashed line) as input data to recalibrate the multiscale model and adjust subsequent treatments, enabling personalized, actionable decisions.

2.2 *In silico* neurology

Nowadays, due to the ageing of the population, neurological disorders are recognized as the second leading cause of death [173]. Indeed, just the disorders affecting the human brain account for 13% of the total disease spectrum [174]. The term “neuro” pertains to nerve cells, while “logia” refers to study; neurological disorders are hence any disease of the nervous systems. Indeed, neurology encompasses diagnosing and treating all states and diseases affecting the nervous system. Instead, “degeneration” refers to the deterioration of tissues or organs, leading to a loss of structure or function. Consequently, neurodegeneration can be described as a progressive decline in both the functionality and structure of neurons, eventually culminating in death [175]. Figure 4 - (a) shows the mortality rates related to neurological diseases in each country in 2012. Almost 10 million people died in 2019 because of neurological disorders, plus there were 349 million disability-adjusted life years lost (representing the loss of the equivalent of one year of full health) [176], as shown in Figure 4 - (b).

Eric L. Schwartz introduced the term “computational neuroscience” during a conference held in 1985 in California. Up to that moment, various names were used for the field, such as neural modelling, neural networks, and brain theory. The outcome of the conference was documented in the book *Computational Neuroscience*, published in 1990 [177]. The convergence of computational neuroscience and neuronal communication with the advancement of new technology has unlocked a range of potential applications across diverse domains. These encompass healthcare, disease modelling, nanomachinery, pattern recognition, neuron-oriented hardware design, biological behaviour emulation, and data mining [178].

Computational neuroscience also deals with virtual reality [179] and neurorobotics [180]. Moreover, within the spectrum of emerging applications, medical inquiries pertaining to the investigation of pathologies and potential therapeutic interventions have come to the fore. Therefore, today, we can speak of *in silico* neurology, or computational neurology, to describe this computational approach within the realm of medical research [181, 182]. Recent advances have coupled virtual-reality based neurorehabilitation with closed-loop brain-computer interfaces and physiologically realistic simulations, enabling patient-tailored therapy protocols and objective outcome prediction in stroke and motor disorders. These approaches often integrate multimodal data streams (EEG, kinematics, imaging) to adapt interventions in real time [183, 184].

Neuroscience has highly complex large-scale datasets (see [185] for data-sharing issues). Neuroinformatics integrates these data (such as neuroimaging, electrophysiological recordings, and genetic data) and computational tools to collect, organize, analyse, and model neurological information [177]. Over the past few years, multiview learning methodologies—a ML technique—have gained significant popularity, and a considerable number of biomedical neurological applications that utilize multiview data have been documented in the literature, showing the potential of neuroinformatics applications for cutting-edge research problems [186]. In parallel, community standards and platforms (e.g., BIDS and OpenNeuro) plus model-description

languages (e.g., NeuroML) have accelerated reproducibility and reuse by providing interoperable formats for neuroimaging, electrophysiology and multi-scale models; this FAIRification of neuroscience data underpins many successful large-scale and ML studies [187, 188, 189, 190].

In silico studies revealed multiple neurological targets, e.g., microRNAs targets [191] and for the antidepressant molecule ursolic acid [192], identifying novel biomarkers [193]. Singh *et al.* [193] conducted a comprehensive review of contemporary developments in *in silico* methodologies for biomarker discovery and validation. By integrating multi-omics strategies, these *in silico* techniques have demonstrated the capacity to swiftly and accurately identify new biomarkers. Moreover, recent initiatives on constructing extensive genomic databases and predictive computational platforms have streamlined the detection of potentially disease-causing genetic variants linked to rare human complex disorders [194].

The investigations related to the organisation of the brain network, both structural and functional, is one of the main addressed research in this field [177], both at a microscopic level of brain dynamics (i.e., single neurons interconnected by synapses) and at a macroscopic level (i.e., brain regions and elementary processing units interconnected). In this context, neurodevelopment arises as a key player to consider, since understanding the process whereby the nervous system forms in humans is of capital relevance to identify possible defects that may arise during it and lead to disorders. Although neurodevelopment has been studied through the lenses of embryology and developmental biology, mathematics also has a role to play. Due to being a paradigmatic example of collective cell migration, neural crest formation has attracted the interest of mathematical modellers [195, 196]. Neural tube formation has also been studied through mathematical modelling [197]. For a general review on mathematical models of neuronal growth, we refer the reader to [198].

Neuronal modelling falls under the umbrella of computational neuroscience. Its goal is to mathematically capture neuron behaviour by using mathematical equations to approximate important biological parameters. The integrate-and-fire (IF) model, the Hodgkin–Huxley (HH) model, the compartment model, and the 2D reduction model are widely used to model neurons [178].

The IF mechanism is not very complex, allowing the development of relatively simple models [199]. Neurons are modelled by exploiting an RC (Resistor-Capacitor) circuit. The neuron state is characterized by its membrane potential, which evolves according to the neuron’s synaptic inputs. Excitatory and inhibitory inputs increase and decrease, respectively, the membrane potential, while a time constant rules the potential decay toward a resting value in the absence of inputs (leaky neurons). When the potential reaches a threshold, an output spike is generated—the firing of the neuron—which causes the potential to reset at a basal value. A refractory period (the time period of complete inexcitability between depolarization and repolarization) can be explicitly considered. A few variants of the integrate-and-fire models exist, see [200] for a review of IF neuron models.

Figure 4: Neurological disease mortality (a) and disability-adjusted life years lost (b) worldwide. (a) Global distribution of deaths from neurological conditions in 2012. Data grouped by deciles (WHO Global Health Estimates 2012). Map adapted from an image available on Wikimedia Commons (file: Neurological conditions world map-Deaths per million persons-WHO2012.svg). Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0). (b) Age-standardised disability-adjusted life year rates (ASR) attributed to neurological disorders for all ages and both sexes across 204 countries and territories in 2019. Figure adapted from [176].

A highly comprehensive framework for describing neurons is the HH model [201]. Unlike the classical IF model, the HH model considers the complex biophysical properties of ion channels present in the neuronal cell membrane. Its adaptability extends to incorporating any number of ion channels within the membrane. Recognizing the significance of their model, Hodgkin and Huxley were honored with the Nobel Prize in 1963. A system of coupled differential equations characterizing the dynamics of ion channel conductances, membrane capacitance, and the movement of ions across the membrane rule the model dynamics [178].

Neurons exhibit dendrites with diverse shapes and spatial arrangements, which are pivotal in shaping the neuron’s input and output characteristics. The compartment model approach serves as a valuable tool to explore how dendrite shape and structure impact the neuron’s behaviour [178].

The HH model, renowned for its complexity, presents challenges in both analysis and visualization. In contrast, the simpler IF model assumes an action potential is triggered when the neuron’s potential reaches a constant threshold. However, certain observations are in opposition to this concept. For instance, using longer pulse currents for stimulation reduces the firing threshold, while shorter pulses increase it. Moreover, data-driven evidence suggests that the firing threshold potential depends on changes in neuron current during a step jump. To explore and understand neuron behaviours, it becomes necessary to condense the four nonlinear differential equations of the HH model into two: the 2D reduction model.

The HH model offers greater empirical detail compared to any IF model, providing predictions about ionic currents and spike shape. Nevertheless, these predictions do not hold up against empirical observations. This outcome is not entirely unexpected, considering that spikes initiate in the axon, a factor not addressed by the single-compartment model. The surprising aspect is that the IF model, even with channel properties from patch-clamp measurements, turns out to be more realistic than the HH model when predicting neuronal spiking responses, particularly at high input frequencies [202].

The inherent complexity and high-dimensional parameter space of classical biophysical models, such as the IF and HH frameworks, have traditionally hindered their calibration from experimental data. However, models based on data science, statistics, and ML are seeing a surge in popularity due to the increasing availability and quality of neural data [203]. Recently, coupling these frameworks with modern ML has emerged as a powerful strategy to overcome parameter estimation challenges while maintaining biophysical interpretability [204]. Within this landscape, supervised methods provide a spectrum of tools to capture neuronal dynamics: from simple Linear Regression [204] and complex support vector machines with radial basis function kernels [205, 206], to random forest and gradient boosting machines, which offer a crucial balance between predictive power and interpretability [204]. Complementing these are advanced signal analysis techniques such as the Frequency Modulated Möbius (FMM) approach and Fourier methods, which utilize amplitude-frequency decompositions [207] to accurately fit diverse oscillatory patterns [208]. Specifically, the multicomponent FMM model has demonstrated significant potential in neuroscience for deciphering complex signals [209], with proven applications in automatic signal analysis [210]. This synergy is further advanced by physics-informed machine learning and differentiable frameworks like Jaxley, which embed mechanistic knowledge into data-driven architectures [211, 212] to estimate latent physiological variables from noisy recordings [213]. By bridging the gap between mechanistic modelling and data-driven discovery, these hybrid approaches ensure that identified parameters remain biologically meaningful and clinically trustworthy [214].

In [20], we use IF models to develop the first model of periodic leg movement, a sensory disorder present in many neurological diseases (for example, in restless legs syndrome), exploiting the IF model.

Neuron networks are studied from the perspective of communication engineering in neural communication. Indeed, information theory is exploited to characterize the neuron network features. This includes understanding the error rate in information transmission within the network, determining the theoretical maximum information capacity of neuron networks, and identifying constraints imposed by the network on the flow of information [178]. Moreover, time-aware approaches to Information Theory uncover compelling evidence for the significance of processes (in contrast to states) in neural functioning, opening the way to generalized Information Theory [215]. All functions within the body, whether voluntary or involuntary, the origins of mental disorders, and any other aspects of brain activity, depend on the intricate operations of the neural network. Understanding this network requires knowledge of the communication process between neurons, commonly referred to as neuro-spike communication [216].

For identifying connectivity patterns, see [217] for a review of the applications of Graph Theory to human brain networks. More recently, GNNs and dynamic graph models have extended classical graph-theoretic approaches by enabling end-to-end learning directly on brain graphs (structural or functional), improving diagnostic classification and allowing discovery of distributed patterns that are not accessible via pairwise statistics [218, 219]. Advanced fusion mechanisms enable us to combine these GNNs with entropy-guided space state models, to help us handle complex, multiscale biological data in neuroscience [124].

The brain, a key argument in neurological research, is an incredibly complex neuronal network and has also received much attention from *in silico* community, for example, see [220, 221, 222, 223, 224]. Indeed, we have witnessed a remarkable upsurge in large-scale initiatives and projects dedicated to the mapping, modelling, simulation, and creation of atlases for the human brain. Notable among these are endeavours such as the Human Brain Project, the BRAIN Initiative, the Human Connectome Project, the Blue Brain Project, the Big Brain, the Allen Brain Atlas, and the Brainnetome, to name a few [225]. Nowadays, it is possible to exploit cloud services to perform brain simulation, such as EBRAINS [226]. The simulations of brain function enable researchers to study brain dynamics under normal and disordered conditions. These simulations provide a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms causing neurological disorders and help develop targeted therapies.

Large-scale simulators (e.g., The Virtual Brain) and cloud infrastructures permit the construction of subject-specific whole-brain models that combine individual connectivity, regional dynamics, and biophysical constraints; such models support hypothesis testing, virtual lesioning, and *in silico* trials of stimulation protocols, forming a bridge toward personalised neuromodulation strategies [220, 227, 228].

Computational neuroanatomy, the *in silico* modelling of brain anatomy, characterizes brain shape and neuroanatomical configuration, helping to understand the structural organisation of the brain and how it

relates to neurological disorders [229]. This includes the construction of brain atlases and the analysis of brain connectivity. G. Hickok combined psycholinguistic and motor control techniques for speech production, developing a hierarchical state feedback control model based on neuroanatomy [230]. The interested reader on baby brain neuroanatomy could refer to Li *et al.*'s review [231].

Neuroimaging analysis applies *in silico* techniques to analyse and process neuroimaging data, such as magnetic resonance imaging, functional magnetic resonance imaging, and positron emission tomography scans. Müller and colleagues provided some practical rules to follow in meta-analysis [232]. Instead, in [233], reproducibility is addressed. These methods aid in identifying patterns of brain activity and structural changes associated with different neurological conditions, such as eating in healthy [234] and disorder-affected [235] subjects, neurorehabilitation [183], emotion [236], and neuropsychiatric disorders [237].

Additionally, advances in deep learning have improved feature extraction and classification from neuroimaging, but concerns about interpretability and generalisability motivate hybrid pipelines that combine mechanistic models with data-driven components [238, 190].

Many complex diseases are investigated in computational neuroscience exploiting multiscale models. Lytton *et al.* perform an excellent clinical-oriented review covering epilepsy, traumatic brain injury, ischemic disease, neurorehabilitation, drug addiction, schizophrenia and neurostimulation [239]. Zang and colleagues discuss probabilistic methods adopted in Computational Neuroscience [240]. Lustoza Rodrigues *et al.* [241] highlights the importance of utilizing computational methods, including quantitative structure-activity relationship prediction models, molecular docking, pharmacokinetic models, and molecular dynamics. Additionally, it showcases potential multi-target drug candidates. Multiscale and hybrid frameworks are now being used to build digital twins of the brain—personalised, mechanistic computational avatars that integrate patient data across scales (molecular to systems) and can be used to test interventions *in silico* before clinical application [242, 243].

Finally, important neurological disorders are highly investigated computationally. For example, Alzheimer's disease [244] and Parkinson's disease [19], two of the main neurodegenerative illnesses, have been investigated by exploiting *in silico* approaches. In general, the main computational contributions are achieved thanks to the analyses of complex neurological data, model simulations and analyses, and identifying potential targets for therapeutic interventions.

2.3 *In silico* epidemiology

When a higher-than-expected occurrence of an illness or health-related events within a community or region is observed, the experts say that an epidemic has begun. When an epidemic disseminates globally, it is designated as a pandemic. Epidemics have been extremely influential events, probably changing the history and course of humanity, e.g., the ancient plagues, the decline of the Han empire in the third century China,

the almost 50% European population demise (estimated in 50 million people) caused by the Black Death in the fourteenth century, and the Aztec defeat by the Spanish empire in the sixteenth century [7]. In 2019, more than thirteen and half million people worldwide died from infectious diseases, almost one-third of which co-happened with non-communicable diseases (i.e., not spread through infection or through other people, but are typically caused by unhealthy behaviours) [245]. Figure 5 shows the infectious and parasitic diseases death rate per million people in 2023 worldwide.

Figure 5: Global distribution of deaths from infectious and parasitic diseases per million persons in 2023. The rates are age-standardised to enable comparisons between countries and over time. Data source: WHO Mortality Database (2025). It should be noted that not all deaths in each country may have been registered with a specified cause of death. Figure adapted from [246].

Nowadays, the effects of infectious diseases in real life, such as social distancing, business and educational closing, increased levels of anxiety, depression, poverty, crime, and domestic violence, in addition to health consequences [247], have been highly understood worldwide because of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 experience also highlighted the crucial role of near real-time digital data streams (mobility, digital contact traces, health-care occupancy, and participatory surveillance) in enabling faster model updates and more targeted interventions [248, 249, 250]. At the same time, the pandemic exposed limitations in model communication and uncertainty quantification, fueling a movement towards ensemble forecasting and clearer uncertainty reporting in public health decision support [251, 21]. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has caused more than 7.1 million confirmed deaths worldwide (as of November 2025), with the majority occurring in the first two years—over 5.5 million deaths by January 2022 [252].

Epidemiological models [253, 254] are fundamental for understanding epidemic evolution and optimal

control strategies to deploy limited resources when epidemics occur in various interconnected areas [255, 256, 257]. Researchers from diverse fields have employed various mathematical techniques and computational tools to study epidemic diffusion in human societies, utilizing methodologies that span differential equations, agent-based models, stochastic processes, statistical analysis, graph theory, ML, AI, computer simulations, geographic information systems, and high-performance computing [8]. This interdisciplinary approach has led to the development of mathematical and computational frameworks for epidemic modelling, integrating epidemiology with mathematics, sociology, management science, control theory, network science, and computer science. Note that these approaches go beyond infectious diseases because they can be applied to describe a general reaction-diffusion process, for example, the spread of innovations, fake news, or computer viruses. In particular, modern computational epidemiology increasingly couples mechanistic transmission models with heterogeneous data (genomes, mobility, clinical records, wastewater, and social-media signals) to improve inference on transmission chains, variant emergence, and spatial spread [258, 248]. These hybrid pipelines allow real-time phylogeographic analyses and phylodynamic-informed forecasts that were not commonplace prior to the Covid-19 pandemic [258]. The motivations for improving *in silico* approaches to epidemiology are multiple [259]. Future pandemics pose challenges due to emerging trends, such as an ever-more-connected (e.g., urbanization, trade, and travel) [260] and digital [261] world, aging population, and immune vulnerabilities. Public health epidemiology must comprehend the complex systems derived from the coevolution of epidemics, social interactions, behaviours [262], and policies. Essential are mathematical models, big data [23], and real-time capabilities to support decisions during epidemics [7]. Additionally, the community has prioritised improving transparency, reproducibility, and model comparison (benchmarking), as well as building robust ensemble forecast systems that combine disparate model types to increase reliability for policymakers [21].

Epidemiological models can be categorized into three broad classes: compartmental models, (complex) network models, and agent-based models [8]. Especially the latter two approaches are developed exploiting the *in silico* framework [7]. Table 2 compares the three approaches, highlighting their strengths and limitations.

Arguably, Bernoulli developed the first mathematical epidemiological models [7, 8]. Compartmental approaches primarily focus on capturing macroscopic trends [263]. They employ assumptions such as population homogeneity and a well-mixed environment to portray epidemic spread at a general level. These models simplify the intricate process of epidemic propagation by considering only essential factors, which are represented through parameters with average values in equations. While this allows mathematical models to analyse overarching trends and characteristics (e.g., basic reproduction number and epidemic threshold), they may lack the nuanced details required to capture the intricate nature of epidemic spread. Deterministic and stochastic epidemic models are two broad subclasses of mathematical models.

Table 2: Comparative summary of mathematical and computational modelling paradigms in epidemiology.

Model class	Approach	Strength	Limitation
Compartmental	Markov chain; ODEs	High analytical tractability; calculation of thresholds (R_0).	Assumes a homogeneous and “well-mixed” population.
Complex networks	Graph theory	Captures contact structures and spatial dissemination patterns; describes metapopulations.	Requires high-resolution data on human mobility and connectivity.
Agent-based	Bottom-up simulations	Accounts for individual heterogeneity and emergent behaviours.	High computational cost; challenges in parameter calibration.

Deterministic compartmental models divide the population into compartments, or classes, grouping individuals based on their health states. The compartments are assumed well-mixed and homogeneous. ODEs rule the transitions between different compartments, corresponding to changes in the individual health states. The most famous and simple formulations are the SIR (Susceptible, Infectious, and Recovered) model and the SIS (Susceptible, Infectious, and Susceptible) model.

Instead, stochastic epidemic models are developed by exploiting stochastic techniques, such as Markov Chains and the Monte Carlo method [264]. The Reed-Frost model is extensively utilized, such as in [265]. It describes the infection process between individuals as a binomial stochastic process, making specific assumptions about a closed population, all having equal contact opportunities. In each (discrete) time step, susceptible individuals can be infected by infectious individuals. The latter then become immune. Formulas allow the computation of flows into infectious and immune compartments. The process is reiterated until the entire population achieves immunity or there are no longer individuals capable of spreading the infection. The model can be iterated multiple times with variations in the starting conditions to investigate their impact on the epidemic course.

Computational methods utilize a diverse array of simulation techniques to offer a more intricate representation of real-world scenarios [8]. These approaches often construct epidemic models based on complex network models [266] and agent-based models [247]. However, the higher level of detail in computational models demands significant data availability and computational resources. Recent advancements in data accessibility and affordable high-performance computing have facilitated the increased use of computational methods to study the propagation of epidemics [261, 23, 259]. Concurrently, improvements in software infrastructure (open-source pipelines, cloud compute, and reproducible workflows) and in standardized data-sharing platforms have reduced barriers to deploying large-scale *in silico* experiments and rapid scenario analysis [248, 258].

The past decade has been marked by a significant improvement in (complex) network-structured epidemiological models. These models exploit networks to describe individuals or populations (network nodes) and their interactions (network edges). Generally, these complex network models can be categorized into two main groups: mean-field models (focusing on the spreading dynamics within complex networks) and networked models (focusing on numerical simulations of epidemics in such networks) [8].

In the spreading dynamics models, the mean-field theory is employed to analyse complex networks, and then differential equations are formulated to describe the propagation of epidemics [8]. Like compartmental models, individuals in these complex network models are classified into different groups based on their health status. In homogeneous networks, the infectious node infectivity is derived from the average node degree, while in heterogeneous networks, nodes are further separated into subgroups based on their degrees [8].

Instead, numerical simulations in complex networks employ ODEs or AB models to represent contact patterns and infection spreads along the links.

On the one hand, simulations with ODEs models typically focus on homogeneous groups (compartments) of people, calculating the aggregated numbers of individuals that are in each state (e.g., susceptible, infected, and resistant) as a function of time. The population is divided into geographical areas, where local infections are governed by the ODEs that rule the people flows among the different model compartments (belonging to the same geographical area) based on the current model state. Thus, the network structure divides and interconnects the populations into regions, forming a network of sub-populations, with the connections between them representing the movement of individuals through transportation and mobility infrastructures and allowing the infection spreads [263, 267, 264].

On the other hand, simulations with AB models typically focus on heterogeneous individuals (with agent-specific characteristics), the network nodes, interacting through the network links. Among subsequent (discrete) time steps, probabilistic procedural rules update the health state of each agent (e.g., susceptible, infected, and resistant) based on the current agent state and the state of its neighbour (linked) agents. Thus, AB models are stochastic, discrete in time, and spatially explicit [268, 247].

A significant focus of most epidemiological network-based models lies in understanding the impact of network topologies on the spread of the disease, particularly on networks such as small-world and scale-free networks. Researchers have also explored epidemic spread within weighted networks and adaptive networks in recent years, leading to intriguing insights into the dynamics of epidemics in various network structures [263, 8]. Recent work has also integrated fine-grained mobility networks into metapopulation SEIR (with Susceptible, Exposed, Infectious and Recovered compartments) frameworks to explain inequities in exposure risk and to identify high-impact locations for interventions (e.g., specific points of interest that drive disproportionate transmission) [249].

In recent times, there has been a growing interest in delving deeper into the intricate evolutionary process

of how epidemics spread, driven by an enhanced comprehension of the broader patterns in epidemic diffusion. As a result, there is an increasing demand for epidemic models that can provide a more nuanced and precise representation of the complex realities involved. Thus, with the goal of developing more realistic models, the AB framework is exploited [8].

Indeed, AB models have the great (potential) advantage of capturing the heterogeneity in individual attributes and behaviours, and also accounting for the stochastic nature inherent in epidemic spreads. By adopting a bottom-up approach, AB modelling places focus on a faithfully detailed representation of the behaviour and interactions among individuals, the micro-level, which ultimately leads to the emergence of the macro-level phenomena associated with the spread of the epidemic [269, 268, 247].

It is essential to note that, as usual, the AB framework leads to certain challenges: here, data availability and computational complexity. However, the ongoing progress in computational capabilities, the increasing availability of data, and the development of sophisticated computational algorithms have significantly boosted the popularity of agent-based models in gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics behind the spread of epidemics [269, 268, 247]. Nevertheless, these advantages must be balanced with rigorous calibration, sensitivity analysis, and methods to quantify structural uncertainty—areas that have seen substantial methodological development during and after the Covid-19 pandemic [251, 21].

It is essential to underline that there is no perfect, correct, or superior modelling approach to transmission dynamics for infectious diseases in general. The model choice depends on factors such as the available data, the specific research question, the time and space scales of the study, and other relevant disease-specific considerations [267]. Commonly exploited methodologies include highly detailed agent-based models and large-scale spatial metapopulation models, i.e., ODEs network-structured models [266]. Indeed, the importance of spatial modelling has been recognized, especially in an integrated approach for early detection and intervention during epidemics [270].

Many different models have been developed to study specific infectious diseases, e.g., influenza [269], West Nile virus [268], tuberculosis [284], bacterial [285], HIV [286], and pertussis [271]. Also, the toolbox has expanded to include genomic phylodynamics for pathogen surveillance (tracking variants and transmission chains) and wastewater-based epidemiology as complementary indicators for community-level infection trends [258].

During a pandemic, decision-making by local, national, and global public health authorities involves critical resource allocation. These resources go beyond routine disease monitoring, focusing on tracking and controlling potential pandemic outbreaks. This allocation hinges on two key factors: estimating the severity risk posed by the infectious pathogen and evaluating the likelihood of the outbreak reaching a specific region and causing widespread, severe illness [7]. Unfortunately, precise risk assessment, especially during the early pandemic stages, is highly challenging. Thus, the significance of modelling and decision support systems in

Table 3: Summary of discussed references categorized by model type, disease, and focus on optimal strategies. *Abbreviations:* Comp.: Compartmental, CN: Complex Network, AB: Agent-Based.

Ref.	Model Type	Disease	Optimal Strategy	Notes
[271]	Comp.	Pertussis	No	Stochastic Petri Nets for age-structured vaccination strategies.
[272]	Comp.	COVID-19	No	SIRD model for forecasting case fatality and recovery rates.
[265]	Comp.	General	No	Extension of Reed-Frost models to random graphs.
[273]	Comp.	Tuberculosis	Yes	Discrete age-structured model for child/adult populations.
[274]	Comp.	General	Yes	SIS model numerical solution for optimal control (treatment/vaccination).
[255]	Comp.	HIV	Yes	Optimal resource allocation across independent populations.
[275]	Comp.	Fungi	Yes	Management of fungicide mixtures to control resistance.
[276]	Comp.	COVID-19	Yes	Feedback control of epidemic stability via daily testing reports.
[250]	Comp.	COVID-19	Yes	Transmission timing and impact of digital contact tracing.
[277]	Comp.	COVID-19	Yes	SEIR model with behavioural changes and governmental actions.
[22]	Comp. / CN	COVID-19	Yes	Timing of one-shot interventions in metapopulations.
[278]	Comp. / CN	COVID-19	Yes	Pro rata vs. optimal vaccine allocation via economic modelling.
[25]	Comp. / CN	COVID-19	Yes	Global metapopulation with ARX feedback for vaccine access.
[249]	CN	COVID-19	No	Metapopulation SEIR with dynamic mobility networks in US cities.
[256]	CN	General	Yes	Metapopulation control directing treatment to low-prevalence regions.
[257]	CN	General	Yes	Allocation across regions balancing efficiency and equity.
[279]	CN	COVID-19	Yes	Network model for intermittent decentralized regional lockdowns.
[280]	CN	COVID-19	Yes	Spatiotemporal resource allocation via network discovery.
[281]	CN	COVID-19	Yes	Semidefinite programming for curing rates in arbitrary networks.
[282]	CN	COVID-19	Yes	Global metapopulation model on equitable vaccine sharing.
[283]	CN	COVID-19	Yes	Spatially explicit model assessing Italian containment measures.
[269]	AB	Influenza A	No	ABM addressing ecology and evolution of polymorphic pathogens.
[284]	AB	Tuberculosis	No	ABM focusing on age-structure and progression stages.

analyzing alternative scenarios becomes increasingly paramount. Various works have been proposed in the literature addressing optimal resource control during epidemics, for example, see [274, 273, 22, 280, 275, 281] for recent studies. Complementary to optimal control, fast scenario-generation and robust decision-making under deep uncertainty (including model ensembles and stress tests) have been emphasised as practical approaches to guide tactical and strategic choices [21].

Focusing on the well-known Covid-19 pandemic, many compartmental models extending the well-known SIR model have been proposed for the Covid-19 pandemic, e.g., [277, 283, 272, 279, 276]. This modelling approach is reasonably predictive [287] for infectious diseases that are transmitted among humans. A few works specifically investigated the effect of different Covid-19 vaccine allocation strategies via a model-informed approach [282, 278]. In particular, [282] analyse the effect of an equitable distribution of the

vaccine doses administrated during 2021, while [278] studies the advantage of using an infection-dependent allocation strategy of the vaccines with respect to a constant one.

In [288], we propose an extended version of the model proposed by Gatto *et al.* [283] at a global scale, including vaccinations and contact-tracing with new certified cases. An extended work also includes an autoregressive-exogenous (ARX) model to deduce the containment measures of national governments based on hospital occupancy [25]. We investigate optimal vaccine allocation strategies by varying both vaccine availability and their distribution. We conclude that to stop Covid-19 (and similar) pandemic, we obviously need to increase vaccine access, but interestingly, this increase is less severe if global equitable access is granted (i.e., proportionally to population size).

To bring this section to a close, in Table 3 we refer to the most relevant works discussed in this section. For each work listed, we specify the type of model employed, the diseases considered, whether the authors evaluated optimal strategies, and a brief note highlighting the main focus of the work.

2.4 Shared paradigms and bottlenecks: cross-disciplinary synthesis

The comparative analysis of oncology, neurology, and epidemiology reveals a profound methodological convergence that transcends the specific biological and scales of each field. Although the biological problems and clinical questions differ, the underlying mathematical structures are remarkably similar: all three domains deal with heterogeneous data, nonlinear dynamics, multiscale interactions, partial observability, and uncertainty-driven decision-making. In this sense, *in silico* modelling is not merely a domain-specific tool, but a unifying framework for extracting mechanistic insight, integrating multi-source information, and guiding intervention design across complex biomedical systems. Specifically, we first introduce the theoretical paradigm (Section 2.4.1), then its practical implementations (Section 2.4.2) and shared pillars (Section 2.4.1). We conclude by highlighting universal bottlenecks in Section 2.4.4.

A graphical representation of the shared paradigms is given in Figure 6, from patient data acquisition to complex-systems modelling, predictive simulation, and clinical translation, while also highlighting the main methodological bottlenecks that limit current implementations.

2.4.1 The Systems and Control foundation

A unifying analytical framework for these three domains is provided by Systems and Control theory. In each field, the modelling objective has shifted from descriptive observation to active system steering: that is, from passive characterization of dynamics to the design of feedback-driven interventions acting on partially observed, nonlinear, and often stochastic systems [289, 290, 161].

In oncology, the use of evolutionary double binds [53, 155, 157] and adaptive therapies [152, 291, 161, 158, 163, 159] aims to steer the tumour-host system toward a stable state, ideally a cancer free equilibrium,

Figure 6: Shared paradigms and bottlenecks. The top panel shows a cross-disciplinary Systems and Control architecture, linking multi-source patient data via hybrid modelling and digital twins to clinical applications. Central to this is the feedback control loop, where predictive simulations drive adaptive treatments, which subsequently generate new clinical data used to refine the intervention. The bottom panels use bottleneck indicators to categorize structural and operational obstacles—ranging from data heterogeneity and numerical stiffness to practical identifiability and clinician skepticism—that must be addressed to ensure robust clinical translation.

typically preventing or delaying the emergence of resistant clones [292, 144, 293, 154, 84]. These strategies explicitly exploit eco-evolutionary dynamics, where treatment acts as a selective pressure shaping tumour composition over time, thus requiring control approaches that incorporate evolutionary game theory and population dynamics [156, 162]. In neurology, closed-loop neurostimulation and brain-computer interfaces act as real-time feedback controllers to restore homeostatic neural activity [294, 295] in disorders such as Parkinson’s disease [296] and psychiatric disorders [297]. In epidemiology, adaptive vaccine allocation and non-pharmaceutical interventions are designed as optimal control problems to stabilize population-level transmission dynamics during outbreaks [22, 25].

Beyond these parallels, an emerging unifying perspective is provided by evolutionary control theory, which extends classical control frameworks to systems in which the state dynamics are shaped by selection, adaptation, and competition [298, 299]. In oncology, this perspective is already central, but it is increasingly relevant in epidemiology through the control of pathogen evolution (e.g., vaccine escape or resistance), and in neurology through adaptive processes such as synaptic plasticity and network reorganisation.

This common logic suggests that advances in one field—such as evolution-aware control algorithms in cancer—can provide a blueprint for managing pathogen evolution in the other areas [299]. More generally, this cross-fertilization highlights that control strategies designed under a systems perspective are often transferable across scales and domains, provided that the underlying dynamical structure is preserved. In addition, successful modelling approaches in one field are derived in other field; for instance, see [300] for the application of an epidemic spreading model to neurology, and [301] for the use of a SIR-like model in oncology. This methodological transfer reinforces the view of a shared mathematical backbone underpinning seemingly disparate biomedical problems.

2.4.2 Hybrid modelling and digital twins

Biological systems are inherently multiscale, as they encompass processes ranging from the molecular to the population level. No single methodology can represent them accurately and effectively on its own. In this context, the hybrid paradigm has emerged to integrate complementary approaches, linking scales through effective interactions, reduced-order representations, or coarse-grained variables [302, 303]. This integration often combines mechanistic, physics-based formulations with data-driven techniques, such as ML, to leverage high-dimensional data while enforcing consistency with biological principles. By embedding learning components within structured dynamical systems—often referred to as physics-informed learning—hybrid models improve generalization and interpretability, which is particularly critical in biomedical applications where data are frequently sparse, noisy, or heterogeneous [304, 211].

This hybrid foundation is central to the digital twin (DT) paradigm. A DT is a patient-specific computational model that integrates mechanistic knowledge with multiscale data to simulate biological evolution under both physiological and pathological conditions. Unlike static models, DTs can be adaptive, closed-loop systems continuously updated through data assimilation to refine predictions over time [305, 306]. Within this framework, the twin acts as a predictive surrogate, enabling the design of personalized interventions through control-theoretic approaches [307]. Furthermore, hybrid DTs facilitate structured uncertainty quantification, combining probabilistic inference with mechanistic constraints to provide the reliable predictions necessary for clinical decision support [308, 309].

The application of hybrid DTs across diverse domains addresses the shared need to model complex, non-linear interactions and feedback loops. In oncology, DTs integrate intracellular signaling, tumour dynamics, and PK/PD to optimise dosing and predict resistance [310]. Recent developments also incorporate evolutionary and eco-dynamic principles to guide adaptive therapy strategies [161]. In neurology, personalized whole-brain models link structural and functional connectivity with dynamical systems to predict disease progression and neuromodulation responses [311, 312, 242, 243]. Finally, in epidemiology, DTs couple host and population dynamics [313]. By combining mobility data and immunological states, these multilevel

models serve as data-driven simulators for real-time surveillance and scenario analysis during outbreaks [314, 315].

Despite their potential, hybrid DTs face challenges regarding model identifiability, computational complexity, and the trade-off between biological realism and transparency, which will be further discussed in the context of cross-disciplinary bottlenecks (Section 2.4.4). Addressing these hurdles is critical for translating these integrative strategies into robust, clinically validated tools across biomedical domains [305, 306].

2.4.3 Shared methodological pillars

The convergence of oncology, neurology, and epidemiology within the *in silico* framework rests upon four foundational methodological pillars that translate biological complexity into actionable mathematical models.

First, the network-based paradigm provides a universal language to describe interactions across scales. Whether modelling intracellular signaling pathways and gene regulatory circuits in oncology [11, 94], the structural and functional connectome in neurology [239], or the contact structures of metapopulations in epidemiology [8, 283], network science identifies the topological determinants of system behaviour. Despite the vast differences in physical scale—from biomolecules to global networks—properties such as small-world, scale-free distributions, and dynamical processes like synchronization or diffusion remain the core drivers of system resilience and pathogen spread.

Second, the data-informed paradigm bridges these structural representations with real-world observations. Rather than replacing physics-based approaches, this paradigm leverages high-dimensional data (imaging, omics, spatial data) to refine parameter estimation and calibrate model structures. Central to this paradigm is mechanistic learning, where data-driven components are constrained by governing equations or biological priors [211, 304]. This integration ensures that models remain adaptive and personalized while maintaining biological plausibility and interpretability, a strategy now foundational across biomedical domains [316, 317, 172, 105].

Third, the complexity paradigm addresses the emergent behaviours that arise from these networked and data-informed systems. AB models serve as the primary tool for exploring this bottom-up complexity, simulating how simple individual-level rules—be it single-cell interactions in oncology [141], neuronal firing in neurology [239], or human mobility in epidemiology [247]—scale up to shape macro-level phenomena such as clonal selection, neural oscillations, or epidemic trajectories (see Tables 1 and 3). Understanding these emergent dynamics is a prerequisite for effective system manipulation.

Finally, the feedback control paradigm transforms these insights into a rigorous framework for designing targeted and adaptive interventions. In oncology, this is exemplified by adaptive therapies that use tumour response as a feedback signal to adjust dosing and prevent resistance [152, 154, 158]. This logic extends to neurology through closed-loop neurostimulation systems that monitor brain activity in real-time to suppress

pathological states [5], and to epidemiology, where control-theoretic approaches optimise vaccine allocation and non-pharmaceutical interventions based on dynamic transmission rates and hospital occupancy [22, 25]. By closing the loop between observation and action, this pillar provides the operational link to the formal systems and control foundations of *in silico* personalized medicine.

2.4.4 Universal bottlenecks

The advancement of *in silico* medicine is hindered by a set of shared structural and operational obstacles that span across oncology, neurology, and epidemiology. The first and most prominent is the multiscale integration bottleneck. Bridging the gap between molecular-level events—such as DNA mutations, synaptic signaling, or pathogen evolution—and organism- or population-level outcomes remains computationally daunting. High-fidelity frameworks, including hybrid PDE-AB models in oncology (H in Table 1), HH frameworks in neurology, and AB models in epidemiology (Table 2), often suffer from numerical stiffness due to the vast differences in temporal and spatial scales. This disparity forces a constant trade-off between biological realism and computational tractability, necessitating more sophisticated coarse-graining techniques and surrogate modelling.

The second barrier lies in data integration and standardization. Despite the abundance of omics and imaging data, these often provide only snapshots that lack the longitudinal resolution required to calibrate truly dynamic models [1]. Furthermore, significant heterogeneity arising worldwide from different hospitals, devices, or acquisition protocols complicates the creation of cohesive datasets [28]. This fragmentation leads to critical issues in parameter inference and model identifiability, manifesting at two distinct levels. While a model might be structurally identifiable in theory—meaning its equations allow for unique parameter solutions under ideal conditions—it often fails the test of practical identifiability due to the limitations of real-world clinical data [318]. When datasets are sparse, noisy, or not properly integrated, the resulting lack of information prevents the precise estimation of parameters, even in structurally sound models. Optimal experimental design (how much data to collect and when to collect it) that ensures parameter identifiability (permitting confidence in model predictions), while minimizing experimental time and costs should be followed [319]. Otherwise, multiple, divergent parameter sets may yield the same output, hindering the model’s ability to uniquely capture the underlying biological mechanisms. While the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data initiatives provide a vital theoretical roadmap to mitigate these issues, their full-scale clinical implementation still lags behind the requirements of high-performance modelling [320].

Directly linked to these challenges is the computational bottleneck. As models incorporate increasing biological detail—such as 3D spatial structures, stochasticity, or large-scale networks—their cost increases exponentially. Simulating a digital twin of the brain [242, 226], a H model in oncology (Table 1), or a city-scale epidemic [7] requires high-performance computing resources seldom available in clinical settings.

This also limits the application of optimal control theory in high-dimensional spaces [84]. Consequently, the development of accelerated solvers and reduced-order representations, such as mesoscopic simulators [321, 322, 323], is a critical priority for enabling real-time clinical decision support.

The final hurdle is the translational bottleneck, which governs the transition from simulation to practice. Regulatory frameworks for model-informed medical devices are still in their infancy [10]. Beyond legal hurdles, black-box models often face skepticism from clinicians. Overcoming this requires ensuring model interpretability, robustly quantifying uncertainty [21], assessing the probability of toxicity [324], and demonstrating clear cost-benefit advantages over current standards of care [13, 25]. Addressing these multidimensional challenges is essential for the broad adoption and reliability of next-generation *in silico* frameworks.

3 Conclusions

In silico medicine has evolved from a supportive computational tool into a central pillar of modern biomedical research, enabling the systematic investigation of complex diseases across scales, modalities, and disciplines. This work has revisited advances in oncology, neurology, and epidemiology, demonstrating how shared principles, such as systems and control theory, network theory, nonlinear dynamics, and multiscale modelling, provide a unifying framework for understanding, predicting, and intervening in complex biological systems. This endeavor is inherently interdisciplinary, integrating fields from medicine and biology to mathematics, computer science, physics, and engineering. Such synergy is essential, as it transforms theoretical understanding into clinically actionable insights. The mathematical foundations of these frameworks serve as a critical bridge between abstract theory and practical implementation, enabling quantitative reasoning that guides medical decision-making.

Central to this progress is sustained computational innovation. The development of advanced tools and high-performance computing has revolutionized our capacity for large-scale simulation and analysis, making detailed, multi-scale models and near real-time analysis a reality. These capabilities are amplified by data-driven and model-informed approaches. The intelligent integration of mechanistic models, which offer interpretability and causal insight, with data-driven and machine learning techniques enhances predictive power, scalability, and supports robust, transparent decision-making.

The impact of this paradigm is vividly illustrated across key domains:

- In oncology, computational models yield profound insights into tumour growth, treatment response, and the evolution of drug resistance. They enable *in silico* testing of new drugs and regimens, accelerating the path toward personalized therapy.
- In neurology, models such as Integrate-and-Fire and Hodgkin-Huxley allow detailed simulations of neuronal behaviour, advancing the study of neurodegenerative diseases and opening avenues for per-

sonalized neurotherapeutics when combined with clinical data.

- In epidemiology, computational models are indispensable for predicting disease spread, evaluating interventions, and informing public health policy, as recently underscored by global health crises.

Looking ahead, the convergence of high-performance computing, big data analytics, and artificial intelligence promises to further transform biomedical research. Future efforts will likely focus on enhancing model personalization through the development of digital twins, integrating multi-scale data, and improving real-time decision support using closed-loop control strategies. Key to this evolution will be the implementation of adaptive and evolution-aware control strategies to manage disease dynamics, alongside the refinement of explainable and hybrid mechanistic-machine learning workflows. Nevertheless, significant challenges remain, including data heterogeneity and availability, model validation, uncertainty quantification, computational complexity, and ethical considerations regarding data privacy and algorithmic transparency. Addressing these will require continued innovation, investment in infrastructure, and the establishment of collaborative, standardized frameworks.

In summary, *in silico* medicine represents far more than a technological evolution. By enabling a systems-level, quantitative, and integrative approach to health and disease, it constitutes a true paradigm shift, following the vision proposed by the famous physicist and philosopher Thomas Kuhn in his noteworthy book *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* [325], where computation becomes an inseparable component of scientific discovery, clinical translation, and decision-making, poised to tackle the most pressing health challenges of our time.

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Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests.

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